

Fuzzy β - γ -open sets and fuzzy β - γ -open mappings

C. Sivashanmugaraja * †, S. Antony Jerold ‡

Received: 5 June 2021 Accepted: 28 July 2021 Published: 10 August 2021

Abstract

In this paper, we introduce the notions of β - γ -closed sets, β - γ -open maps, β^* - γ -open maps and β - γ -continuity in fuzzy topological spaces. We explore the relationship between open sets, γ -open sets, β -open sets and β - γ -open sets in fuzzy settings. In addition, we explore the relationships between fuzzy β - γ -open and fuzzy β^* - γ -open mappings. We prove that the composition of two fuzzy β^* - γ -open mappings is also a fuzzy β^* - γ -open, while the composition of two fuzzy β - γ -open mappings need not be fuzzy β - γ -open. Some useful and important basic properties of these sets and mappings are also obtained.

1 Introduction

In [6], Zadeh introduced the concept of fuzzy sets. After that fuzzy topological space was introduced by Chang [2]. Fuzzy sets have applications in many fields such as information and control. The concept of an operation γ on fuzzy topological spaces was introduced by Kasahara [4]. By using the concept of an operation γ , Kalitha and Das [3] introduced the concepts of γ -open sets in fuzzy topological spaces. Balasubramanian [1] defined β -open fuzzy sets. Recently Sivashanmugaraja and Vadivel [5] introduced the notions of β - γ -open fuzzy sets which are weaker than γ -open fuzzy sets. In this paper, we introduce the notions of β - γ -closed, β - γ -open maps, β^* - γ -open maps and β - γ -continuous in fuzzy topological spaces. We investigate the relationship between open sets, γ -open sets, β -open sets and β - γ -open sets in fuzzy settings.

2 Preliminaries

In this section, we include certain definitions and known results needed for the subsequent development of the study. Throughout this paper (X, τ) or simply X always mean a fuzzy topological space (fts, for short). By $\underline{0}$ and $\underline{1}$, we mean the constant fuzzy sets taking on the values 0 and 1 on X , respectively.

Definition 1 [4] Let (X, τ) be a fuzzy topological space. A fuzzy operation γ on the topology τ is a mapping from τ into set I^X (family of all subsets of X) such that $V \subset \gamma(V)$ for each $V \in \tau$, where $\gamma(V)$ denotes the value of γ at V . The mapping defined by $\gamma(G) = G$, $\gamma(G) = cl(G)$, $\gamma(G) = int(cl(G))$, etc are some examples of fuzzy operations.

Definition 2 [3] A fuzzy subset λ of (X, τ) is said to be fuzzy γ -open if for each $p_x^\lambda q \lambda$, there exists a $V \in \tau$ and $p_x^\lambda q V$ such that $\gamma(V) \subset \lambda$. τ_γ denotes the set of all fuzzy γ -open sets. Clearly we have $\tau_\gamma \subset \tau$.

Definition 3 [3] Let λ be a fuzzy set in a fts X . Then $\tau_\gamma-cl(\lambda)$ is defined as $\tau_\gamma-cl(\lambda) = \bigwedge \{ \mu : \lambda \leq \mu, \mu^c \in \tau_\gamma(X) \}$ and $\tau_\gamma-int(\lambda)$ is defined as $\tau_\gamma-int(\lambda) = \bigvee \{ \mu : \mu \leq \lambda, \mu \in \tau_\gamma(X) \}$.

Definition 4 [1] A fuzzy subset λ of (X, τ) is said to be fuzzy β -open if $\lambda \leq cl(int(cl(\lambda)))$. The complement of a fuzzy β -open set is said to be fuzzy β -closed.

*Department of Mathematics, Periyar Government Arts College, Cuddalore, Tamil Nadu 607 001, India

†Corresponding author email: csrajamaths@yahoo.co.in

‡Department of Mathematics, Sriram College of Arts and Science, Perumalpattu, Tamil Nadu 602, 024 India

Definition 5 [1] Let λ be a fuzzy set in a fts X . Then the β -interior of λ is defined as $\beta int(\lambda) = \vee\{\mu : \mu \leq \lambda, \mu \in F\beta O(X)\}$ and the β -closure of λ is defined as $\beta cl(\lambda) = \wedge\{\mu : \mu \geq \lambda, \mu \in F\beta C(X)\}$.

Definition 6 [5] A fuzzy subset λ of (X, τ) is said to be fuzzy β - γ -open if $\lambda \leq cl(\tau_\gamma int(cl(\lambda)))$. The family of all fuzzy β - γ -open sets is denoted by $F\beta_\gamma O(X)$.

Definition 7 [2] A mapping $f : (X, \tau_X) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$ is called fuzzy continuous, if $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is fuzzy open set in (X, τ_X) , \forall fuzzy open set λ in (Y, τ_Y) .

3 Fuzzy β - γ -open and Fuzzy β - γ -closed Sets

In this section, we introduce the concept of fuzzy β - γ -closed, fuzzy β - γ -closure and fuzzy β - γ -interior in a fuzzy topological space. Also, we investigate some of their basic properties and characterizations.

Definition 8 A fuzzy subset λ of (X, τ) is said to be fuzzy β - γ -closed if $\lambda \geq int(\tau_\gamma cl(int(\lambda)))$. The family of all fuzzy β - γ -closed sets is denoted by $F\beta_\gamma C(X)$.

Definition 9 Let λ be a fuzzy subset of a fts (X, τ) . Then β - γ -interior of λ is defined as $\beta int_\gamma(\lambda) = \vee\{\mu \leq \lambda : \mu \in F\beta_\gamma O(X)\}$.

Proposition 1 Let X be a fts and $\lambda \leq \mu \leq X$ then

- (i) $\beta int_\gamma(\lambda)$ is a β - γ -open fuzzy set in (X, τ) ;
- (ii) $\beta int_\gamma(\lambda) \leq \lambda$;
- (iii) $\beta int_\gamma(\lambda) \leq \beta int_\gamma(\mu)$;
- (iv) $\beta int_\gamma(\lambda) = \beta int_\gamma(\beta int_\gamma(\lambda))$;
- (v) λ is a β - γ -open fuzzy set iff $\lambda = \beta int_\gamma(\lambda)$.
- (vi) $\beta int_\gamma(0) = 0$; $\beta int_\gamma(1) = 1$;
- (vii) $\beta int_\gamma(\lambda \vee \mu) \geq \beta int_\gamma(\lambda) \vee \beta int_\gamma(\mu)$;
- (viii) $\beta int_\gamma(\lambda \wedge \mu) \leq \beta int_\gamma(\lambda) \wedge \beta int_\gamma(\mu)$.

Definition 10 Let λ be a fuzzy subset of a fts (X, τ) . Then β - γ -closure of λ is defined as $\beta cl_\gamma(\lambda) = \wedge\{\mu \geq \lambda : \mu \in F\beta_\gamma C(X)\}$.

Proposition 2 Let X be a fts and $\lambda \leq \mu \leq X$ then

- (i) $\beta cl_\gamma(\lambda)$ is a β - γ -closed fuzzy set in (X, τ) ;
- (ii) $\beta cl_\gamma(\lambda) \geq \lambda$;
- (iii) $\beta cl_\gamma(\lambda) \leq \beta cl_\gamma(\mu)$;
- (iv) $\beta cl_\gamma(\lambda) = \beta cl_\gamma(\beta cl_\gamma(\lambda))$;
- (v) λ is a β - γ -closed fuzzy set iff $\lambda = \beta cl_\gamma(\lambda)$.
- (vi) $\beta cl_\gamma(0) = 0$; $\beta cl_\gamma(1) = 1$;
- (vii) $\beta cl_\gamma(\lambda \vee \mu) \geq \beta cl_\gamma(\lambda) \vee \beta cl_\gamma(\mu)$;
- (viii) $\beta cl_\gamma(\lambda \wedge \mu) \leq \beta cl_\gamma(\lambda) \wedge \beta cl_\gamma(\mu)$.

Theorem 1 If $\{\lambda_i : i \in \Delta\}$ is a collection of fuzzy β - γ -open sets of a fts X , then $\bigvee_{i \in \Delta}$ is β - γ -open.

Proof. Since $\lambda_i \leq cl(\tau_\gamma\text{-int}(cl(\lambda_i)))$, $\forall i \in \Delta$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \bigvee_{i \in \Delta} [cl(\tau_\gamma\text{-int}(cl(\lambda_i)))] \\ &\leq cl[\bigvee_{i \in \Delta} \tau_\gamma\text{-int}(cl(\lambda_i))] \\ &\leq cl(\tau_\gamma\text{-int}[\bigvee_{i \in \Delta} (cl(\lambda_i))]) \\ &\leq cl(\tau_\gamma\text{-int}(cl(\bigvee_{i \in \Delta} \lambda_i))) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\{\lambda_i : i \in \Delta\}$ is fuzzy β - γ -open. ■

Remark 1 Any finite intersection of fuzzy β - γ -open sets need not be β - γ -open as shown in the following example.

Example 1 Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4 \in I^X$ defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_1(a) &= 0.7, \lambda_1(b) = 0.4, \lambda_1(c) = 0.3; \\ \lambda_2(a) &= 0.5, \lambda_2(b) = 0.1, \lambda_2(c) = 0.8; \\ \lambda_3(a) &= 0.7, \lambda_3(b) = 0.4, \lambda_3(c) = 0.8; \\ \lambda_4(a) &= 0.5, \lambda_4(b) = 0.1, \lambda_4(c) = 0.3. \end{aligned}$$

Let $\tau = \{\underline{1}, \underline{0}, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4\}$. Then clearly (X, τ) is a fts. Define an operation γ on τ by $\gamma(\lambda_1) = \lambda_1$, $\gamma(\lambda_2) = \lambda_2$, $\gamma(\lambda_3) = cl(\lambda_3)$ and $\gamma(\lambda_4) = cl(\lambda_4)$. Then the fuzzy sets λ_1 and λ_2 are fuzzy β - γ -open sets but $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_2 (= \lambda_4)$ is not fuzzy β - γ -open.

Remark 2

- (i) Every fuzzy γ -open sets are fuzzy open;
- (ii) Every fuzzy γ -open sets are fuzzy β - γ -open;
- (iii) Every fuzzy β - γ -open sets are fuzzy β -open;
- (iv) Every fuzzy open sets are fuzzy β -open.

The converse of the above remark 2 need not be true as shown in the following example.

Example 2 Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3 \in I^X$ defined by $\lambda_1 = \underline{0.3}$; $\lambda_2 = \underline{0.6}$; $\lambda_3 = \underline{0.8}$. Let $\tau = \{\underline{1}, \underline{0}, \lambda_1, \lambda_2\}$. Then clearly (X, τ_X) is a fts. Define an operation γ on τ by $\gamma(\lambda_1) = \lambda_1$, $\gamma(\lambda_2) = cl(\lambda_2)$. Then

- (i) The fuzzy set λ_2 is open set but not γ -open.
- (ii) The fuzzy set λ_3 is β - γ -open set but not γ -open.
- (iii) The fuzzy set λ_2 is β -open set but not β - γ -open.
- (iv) The fuzzy set λ_3 is β -open set but not open.

4 Fuzzy β - γ -Open and Fuzzy β^* - γ -Open Mappings

Definition 11 Let (X, τ_X) and (Y, τ_Y) be two fuzzy topological spaces and γ be a fuzzy operation on τ_Y . A mapping $f : (X, \tau_X) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$ is called

- (i) fuzzy β - γ -open, if the image of every open fuzzy set of (X, τ_X) is β - γ -open fuzzy set of (Y, τ_Y) ;
- (ii) fuzzy β - γ -closed, if the image of every closed fuzzy set of (X, τ_X) is β - γ -closed fuzzy set of (Y, τ_Y) .

Definition 12 Let (X, τ_X) and (Y, τ_Y) be two fuzzy topological spaces and γ be a fuzzy operation on τ_X and τ_Y . A mapping $f : (X, \tau_X) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$ is called

- (i) fuzzy β^* - γ -open, if the image of every β - γ -open fuzzy set of (X, τ_X) is β - γ -open fuzzy set of (Y, τ_Y) ;

- (ii) fuzzy β^* - γ -closed, if the image of every β - γ -closed fuzzy set of (X, τ_X) is β - γ -closed fuzzy set of (Y, τ_Y) .

Remark 3 The notions of fuzzy β - γ -open and β^* - γ -open mappings are independent as shown in the following example.

Example 3 Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4 \in I^X$ defined by $\lambda_1 = \underline{0.5}$, $\lambda_2 = \underline{0.7}$, $\lambda_3 = \underline{0.8}$, $\lambda_4 = \underline{0.2}$. Let $\tau_X = \{\underline{1}, \underline{0}, \lambda_1\}$ and $\tau_Y = \{\underline{1}, \underline{0}, \lambda_2, \lambda_3\}$. Then clearly (X, τ_X) and (Y, τ_Y) are fts. Define an operation γ on τ_X by $\gamma(\underline{1}) = \underline{1}$, $\gamma(\underline{0}) = \underline{0}$, $\gamma(\lambda_1) = \lambda_1$ and also define γ on τ_Y by $\gamma(\underline{1}) = \underline{1}$, $\gamma(\underline{0}) = \underline{0}$, $\gamma(\lambda_2) = \lambda_2$, $\gamma(\lambda_3) = cl(\lambda_3)$. Let $f : (X, \tau_X) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$ be an identity mapping. Then f is fuzzy β - γ -open mapping but not fuzzy β^* - γ -open. Since $\lambda_4 \in F\beta_\gamma O(X)$ but $f(\lambda_4) \notin F\beta_\gamma O(Y)$.

Example 4 Let $X = Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4 \in I^X$ defined by $\lambda_1 = \underline{0.1}$, $\lambda_2 = \underline{0.3}$, $\lambda_3 = \underline{0.7}$, $\lambda_4 = \underline{0.8}$. Let $\tau_X = \{\underline{1}, \underline{0}, \lambda_1, \lambda_2\}$ and $\tau_Y = \{\underline{1}, \underline{0}, \lambda_3, \lambda_4\}$. Then clearly (X, τ_X) and (Y, τ_Y) are fts. Define an operation γ on τ_X by $\gamma(\underline{1}) = \underline{1}$, $\gamma(\underline{0}) = \underline{0}$, $\gamma(\lambda_1) = cl(\lambda_1)$, $\gamma(\lambda_2) = cl(\lambda_2)$ and also define γ on τ_Y by $\gamma(\underline{1}) = \underline{1}$, $\gamma(\underline{0}) = \underline{0}$, $\gamma(\lambda_3) = \lambda_3$, $\gamma(\lambda_4) = cl(\lambda_4)$. Let $f : (X, \tau_X) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$ be an identity mapping. Then f is fuzzy β^* - γ -open mapping but not fuzzy β - γ -open. Since λ_1 is an open fuzzy set in X but $f(\lambda_1) \notin F\beta_\gamma O(Y)$.

Definition 13 A mapping $f : (X, \tau_X) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$ is called fuzzy β - γ -continuous, if $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is β - γ -open fuzzy set in (X, τ_X) , \forall open fuzzy set λ in (Y, τ_Y) .

Theorem 2 For a bijective mapping $f : (X, \tau_X) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$, the following statements are equivalent:

- (i) f^{-1} is fuzzy β - γ -continuous;
- (ii) f is fuzzy β - γ -open;
- (iii) f is fuzzy β - γ -closed.

Proof. Follows from the definitions. ■

Theorem 3 Let $f_1 : (X, \tau_X) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$ and $f_2 : (Y, \tau_Y) \rightarrow (Z, \tau_Z)$ be two mappings. If f_1 is an onto fuzzy β - γ -continuous and $(f_2 \circ f_1)$ is fuzzy β^* - γ -closed, then f_2 is fuzzy β - γ -closed.

Proof. Let λ be a closed fuzzy set in Y and f_1 be a fuzzy β - γ -continuous mapping. Therefore $f_1^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a β - γ -closed fuzzy set in X . But $(f_2 \circ f_1)$ is a fuzzy β^* - γ -closed, then $(f_2 \circ f_1)(f_1^{-1}(\lambda))$ is β - γ -closed in Z . Also, by onto of f_1 , $f_2(\lambda)$ is β - γ -closed fuzzy set in Z . Hence, f_2 is fuzzy β - γ -closed. ■

Theorem 4 For a mapping $f : (X, \tau_X) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$, then the following are equivalent:

- (i) f is fuzzy β - γ -closed;
- (ii) $\beta cl_\gamma(f(\lambda)) \leq f(cl(\lambda)) \forall$ fuzzy subset λ of X ;
- (iii) If f is an onto, then \forall subset λ of Y and each open fuzzy set μ in X containing $f^{-1}(\lambda)$, \exists a β - γ -open fuzzy set η of Y containing λ such that $f^{-1}(\eta) \leq \mu$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii) Let $cl(\lambda)$ be a closed fuzzy subset of X . Since f is fuzzy β - γ -closed, $f(cl(\lambda)) \in F\beta_\gamma C(Y)$. Hence, $\beta cl_\gamma(f(\lambda)) \leq f(cl(\lambda))$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i) Let λ be a closed fuzzy subset of X . Then $cl(\lambda) = \lambda$. By hypothesis, $\beta cl_\gamma(f(\lambda)) \leq f(cl(\lambda)) = f(\lambda)$. Hence, $f(\lambda) \in F\beta_\gamma C(Y)$. Therefore, f is fuzzy β - γ -closed.

(i) \Rightarrow (iii) Suppose that $\eta = Y \setminus f(X \setminus \mu)$ and μ is an open fuzzy set of X containing $f^{-1}(\lambda)$. Then by hypothesis, η is β - γ -open fuzzy set in Y . But, $f^{-1}(\lambda) \leq \mu$, then $\lambda \leq f(\mu)$ and $f(X \setminus \mu) \leq Y \setminus \lambda$, that is, $\lambda \leq \eta$ and $f^{-1}(\eta) \leq \mu$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (i) Let ν be a closed fuzzy subset of X and y be any fuzzy point of $Y \setminus f(\nu)$. Then $f^{-1}(y) \in X \setminus \nu$ which is open fuzzy set in X . Hence by hypothesis, \exists a β - γ -open fuzzy set η containing y such that $f^{-1}(\eta) \leq X \setminus \nu$. But f is an onto, then $y \in \eta \leq Y \setminus f(\nu)$ and $Y \setminus f(\nu)$ is the supremum of β - γ -open fuzzy sets and hence, $f(\nu)$ is β - γ -closed fuzzy set in Y . Therefore, f is fuzzy β - γ -closed. ■

Remark 4 The composition of two fuzzy β - γ -open mappings need not be fuzzy β - γ -open as shown in the following example.

Example 5 Let $X = Y = Z = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4, \lambda_5, \lambda_6 \in I^X$ defined by

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda_1(a) &= 0.2, \lambda_1(b) = 0.1, \lambda_1(c) = 0.2; \\ \lambda_2(a) &= 0.3, \lambda_2(b) = 0.5, \lambda_2(c) = 0.1; \\ \lambda_3(a) &= 0.3, \lambda_3(b) = 0.5, \lambda_3(c) = 0.2; \\ \lambda_4(a) &= 0.2, \lambda_4(b) = 0.1, \lambda_4(c) = 0.1. \\ \lambda_5 &= 0.7, \lambda_6 = 0.8.\end{aligned}$$

Let $\tau_X = \{\underline{1}, \underline{0}, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4\}$, $\tau_Y = \{\underline{1}, \underline{0}\}$, and $\tau_Z = \{\underline{1}, \underline{0}, \lambda_5, \lambda_6\}$. Then clearly (X, τ_X) , (Y, τ_Y) and (Z, τ_Z) are fts. Define an operation $\gamma : \tau_Y \rightarrow I^Y$ by $\gamma(\underline{1}) = \underline{1}$, $\gamma(\underline{0}) = \underline{0}$ and also define an operation $\gamma : \tau_Z \rightarrow I^Z$ by $\gamma(\underline{1}) = \underline{1}$, $\gamma(\underline{0}) = \underline{0}$, $\gamma(\lambda_5) = cl(\lambda_5)$, $\gamma(\lambda_6) = \lambda_6$. Let $f_1 : (X, \tau_X) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$ and $f_2 : (Y, \tau_Y) \rightarrow (Z, \tau_Z)$ be two identity mappings. Then clearly, f_1 and f_2 are fuzzy β - γ -open mappings but $(f_2 \circ f_1)$ is not fuzzy β - γ -open. Since, λ_1 is an open fuzzy set of X , but $(f_2 \circ f_1)(\lambda_1) \notin FP_\gamma O(Z)$.

Theorem 5 Let $f_1 : (X, \tau_X) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$ and $f_2 : (Y, \tau_Y) \rightarrow (Z, \tau_Z)$ be two fuzzy β^* - γ -open mappings. Then the composite map $(f_2 \circ f_1) : (X, \tau_X) \rightarrow (Z, \tau_Z)$ is also a fuzzy β^* - γ -open.

Proof. Suppose that λ be a β - γ -open fuzzy set in X . Since, f_1 be a fuzzy β^* - γ -open mapping, we obtain $f_1(\lambda)$ is a β - γ -open fuzzy set in Y . Also by hypothesis f_2 is fuzzy β^* - γ -open, then $f_2(f_1(\lambda))$ is β - γ -open fuzzy set in Z . Also $f_2(f_1(\lambda)) = (f_2 \circ f_1)(\lambda)$. Hence, the composite map $(f_2 \circ f_1)$ is fuzzy β^* - γ -open. ■

We give some other properties of the composition of two fuzzy β - γ -open (resp. fuzzy β - γ -closed) mappings in the following.

Theorem 6 Let $f_1 : (X, \tau_X) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$ and $f_2 : (Y, \tau_Y) \rightarrow (Z, \tau_Z)$. Then the following statements are hold:

- (i) If f_1 is a fuzzy open and f_2 is a fuzzy β - γ -open mappings, then $(f_2 \circ f_1)$ is fuzzy β - γ -open mapping;
- (ii) If $(f_2 \circ f_1)$ is a fuzzy β - γ -open and f_1 is an onto fuzzy continuous map, then f_2 is fuzzy β - γ -open mapping;
- (iii) If $(f_2 \circ f_1)$ is a fuzzy open and f_2 is an one-one fuzzy β - γ -continuous map, then f_1 is fuzzy β - γ -open mapping.

Proof. (i) Let $\lambda \in \tau_X$. Since f_1 is fuzzy open, $f_1(\lambda) \in \tau_Y$. Also since, f_2 is a fuzzy β - γ -open map, $f_2(f_1(\lambda)) \in F\beta_\gamma O(Z)$. Since $(f_2 \circ f_1)(\lambda) = f_2(f_1(\lambda))$, we have $(f_2 \circ f_1)$ is fuzzy β - γ -open mapping.

(ii) Let $\lambda \in \tau_Y$ and f_1 be a fuzzy continuous map. Then $f_1^{-1}(\lambda) \in \tau_X$. Since, $(f_2 \circ f_1)$ is a fuzzy β - γ -open map, $(f_2 \circ f_1)(f_1^{-1}(\lambda)) \in F\beta_\gamma O(Z)$. Hence by onto of f_1 , $f_2(\lambda) \in F\beta_\gamma O(Z)$. Hence, f_2 is fuzzy β - γ -open.

(iii) Let $\lambda \in \tau_X$ and $(f_2 \circ f_1)$ be a fuzzy open map. Then $(f_2 \circ f_1)(\lambda) = f_2(f_1(\lambda)) \in \tau_Z$. By hypothesis, f_2 is an one-one β - γ -continuous map, then $f_2^{-1}(f_2(f_1(\lambda))) = f_1(\lambda) \in F\beta_\gamma O(Y)$. So, f_1 is fuzzy β - γ -open. ■

Theorem 7 Let $f : (X, \tau_X) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$ be a mapping. Then the following are equivalent:

- (i) f is a fuzzy β - γ -continuous mapping;
- (ii) $\beta int_\gamma(\beta cl_\gamma(f^{-1}(\mu))) \leq f^{-1}(cl(\mu))$, \forall fuzzy set μ of Y .
- (iii) $f(\beta int_\gamma(\beta cl_\gamma(\lambda))) \leq cl(f(\lambda))$, \forall fuzzy set λ of X .

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii) Let μ be a fuzzy closed set of Y . Therefore $f^{-1}(cl(\mu))$ is β - γ -closed fuzzy set, thus $f^{-1}(cl(\mu)) \geq \beta int_\gamma(\beta cl_\gamma(f^{-1}(cl(\mu)))) \geq \beta int_\gamma(\beta cl_\gamma(f^{-1}(\mu)))$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii) Let λ be a fuzzy set of X . Take $\mu = f(\lambda)$, then $\lambda \leq f^{-1}(\mu)$. By hypothesis, we get $\beta int_\gamma(\beta cl_\gamma(\lambda)) \leq \beta int_\gamma(\beta cl_\gamma(f^{-1}(\mu))) \leq f^{-1}(cl(\mu))$. Hence, $f(\beta int_\gamma(\beta cl_\gamma(\lambda))) \leq cl(\mu) = cl(f(\lambda))$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (i) Let ν be a closed fuzzy set of Y . By hypothesis, we get $f(\beta int_\gamma(\beta cl_\gamma(f^{-1}(\nu)))) \leq cl(f(f^{-1}(\nu))) \leq cl(\nu) = \nu$. Therefore $\beta int_\gamma(\beta cl_\gamma(f^{-1}(\nu))) \leq f^{-1}f(\beta int_\gamma(\beta cl_\gamma(f^{-1}(\nu)))) \leq f^{-1}(\nu)$. Thus $f^{-1}(\nu)$ is a β - γ -closed fuzzy set. ■

Theorem 8 Let $f : (X, \tau_X) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$ be an one-one and onto mapping. Then f is fuzzy β - γ -continuous iff $\text{int}(f(\lambda)) \leq f(\beta\text{int}_\gamma(\lambda))$, \forall fuzzy set λ of X .

Proof. Suppose that f be a fuzzy β - γ -continuous mapping and let λ be a fuzzy set of X . Therefore $f^{-1}(\text{int}(f(\lambda)))$ is a β - γ -open fuzzy set of X . Since f is an one-one, we obtain $f^{-1}(\text{int}(f(\lambda))) \leq \beta\text{int}_\gamma f^{-1}(\text{int}(f(\lambda))) \leq \beta\text{int}_\gamma f^{-1}f(\lambda) = \beta\text{int}_\gamma \lambda$. Again, since f is onto, we obtain, $\text{int}(f(\lambda)) = f(f^{-1}(\text{int}(f(\lambda)))) \leq f(\beta\text{int}_\gamma \lambda)$.

Conversely, suppose that μ be an open fuzzy set of Y . Therefore $\text{int}(\mu) = \mu$. By hypothesis, $f(\beta\text{int}_\gamma(f^{-1}(\mu))) \geq \text{int}(f(f^{-1}(\mu))) = \text{int}(\mu) = \mu$. This gives that $f^{-1}(f(\beta\text{int}_\gamma(f^{-1}(\mu)))) \geq f^{-1}(\mu)$. Since f is an one-one, we get $\beta\text{int}_\gamma(f^{-1}(\mu)) = f^{-1}(f(\beta\text{int}_\gamma(f^{-1}(\mu)))) \geq f^{-1}(\mu)$. Thus $\beta\text{int}_\gamma(f^{-1}(\mu)) = f^{-1}(\mu)$. Hence f is fuzzy β - γ -continuous. ■

Theorem 9 Let (X, τ_X) and (Y, τ_Y) be two fts and γ be a fuzzy operation on τ_X . Let $f_1 : (X, \tau_X) \rightarrow (Y, \tau_Y)$ and $f_2 : (Y, \tau_Y) \rightarrow (Z, \tau_Z)$ be two mappings. If f_1 is fuzzy β - γ -continuous and f_2 is fuzzy continuous, then $(f_2 \circ f_1)$ is fuzzy β - γ -continuous.

Proof. let λ be an open fuzzy set in Z . Since f_2 is fuzzy continuous, we have $f_2^{-1}(\lambda)$ is open fuzzy set in Y . Again, since f_1 is fuzzy β - γ -continuous, we have $f_1^{-1}(f_2^{-1}(\lambda))$ is β - γ -open fuzzy set in X . Hence $(f_2 \circ f_1)^{-1}(\lambda) = f_1^{-1}(f_2^{-1}(\lambda))$ is fuzzy β - γ -continuous. ■

5 Conclusions

In this work, the notions of fuzzy β - γ -open and fuzzy β^* - γ -open mappings are introduced. Also we introduced the notion of β - γ -continuous mappings. We proved the notions of fuzzy β - γ -open and fuzzy β^* - γ -open mappings are independent. Moreover we have discussed the relationships between these mappings. There is a scope to study and extend these newly defined mappings.

Acknowledgment. The authors would like to thank the anonymous reviewers.

References

- [1] G. Balasubramanian, On Fuzzy β -compact Spaces and Fuzzy β -extremely disconnected Spaces, *Kybernetika.*, 33 (1997), 271-277.
- [2] C. L. Chang, Fuzzy topological spaces, *J. Math. Anal. Appl.*, 24 (1968), 182-189.
- [3] B. Kalita and N. R. Das, Some Aspects of Fuzzy operations, *The Journal of Fuzzy Mathematics*, 19(3) (2011), 531-540.
- [4] S. Kasahara, Operation-Compact spaces, *Math. Japonica*, 24 (1979), 97-105.
- [5] C. Sivashanmugaraaja and A. Vadivel, Weak forms of fuzzy γ -open fuzzy sets, *Global Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics.*, 13 (2017), 251-261.
- [6] L. A. Zadeh, Fuzzy sets, *Information and Control*, 8 (1965), 338-353.

© 2021 by the authors; licensee Further Science, India. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Publisher's Note: Further Science stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.